

True power loss reduction by augmented mine blast algorithm

Kanagasabai Lenin

Department of EEE, Prasad V. Potluri Siddhartha Institute of Technology, India

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, Mine Blast Algorithm (MBA) has been intermingled with Harmony Search (HS) algorithm for solving optimal reactive power dispatch problem. MBA is based on explosion of landmines and HS is based on Creativeness progression of musicians-both are hybridized to solve the problem. In MBA Initial distance of shrapnel pieces are reduced gradually to allow the mine bombs search the probable global minimum location in order to amplify the global explore capability. Harmony search (HS) imitates the music creativity process where the musicians supervise their instruments' pitch by searching for a best state of harmony. Hybridization of Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) improves the search effectively in the solution space. Mine blast algorithm improves the exploration and harmony search algorithm augments the exploitation. At first the proposed algorithm starts with exploration & gradually it moves to the phase of exploitation. Proposed Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) has been tested on standard IEEE 14, 300 bus test systems. Real power loss has been reduced considerably by the proposed algorithm. Then Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) tested in IEEE 30, bus system (with considering voltage stability index)- real power loss minimization, voltage deviation minimization, and voltage stability index enhancement has been attained.

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Corresponding Author:

Kanagasabai Lenin,
Department of EEE,
Prasad V. Potluri Siddhartha Institute of Technology,
Kanuru, Vijayawada, Andhra Pradesh-520007, India.
Email: gklenin@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

In this work the key objective is Actual power loss reduction. Optimal reactive power problem has been solved by a variety of methods [1-6]. However, many technical hitches are found while solving problem due to an assortment of constraints. Evolutionary techniques [7-18] are applied to solve the reactive power problem, but the key problem is some algorithms stuck in local optimal solution & failed to balance the Exploration & Exploitation during the search of global solution. In this paper, Mine Blast Algorithm (MBA) has been intermingled with Harmony Search (HS) algorithm for solving optimal reactive power dispatch problem. MBA is based on explosion of landmines and HS is based on Creativeness progression of musicians-both are hybridized to solve the problem. More first shot points are used and it will increase the initial population. It consequently increases the number of function evaluations and the existing location of a mine bomb. In order to accomplish unvarying search in the domain space the value of θ is set by $360/N_s$ and through this amassing of individuals in a specific region of the area search can be prevented. Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) improves the search effectively in the solution

space. Mine blast algorithm improves the exploration and harmony search algorithm augments the exploitation. At first the proposed algorithm starts with exploration & gradually it moves to the phase of exploitation. Proposed Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) has been tested on standard IEEE 14,300 bus test systems. Real power loss has been reduced considerably by the proposed algorithm. Then Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) tested in IEEE 30, bus system (with considering voltage stability index)- real power loss minimization, voltage deviation minimization, and voltage stability index enhancement has been attained.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Objective of the problem is to reduce the true power loss

$$F = P_L = \sum_{k \in \text{Nbr}} g_k (V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \theta_{ij}) \quad (1)$$

Voltage deviation given as follows

$$F = P_L + \omega_v \times \text{Voltage Deviation} \quad (2)$$

Voltage deviation given by:

$$\text{Voltage Deviation} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{pq}} |V_i - 1| \quad (3)$$

Constraint (Equality)

$$P_G = P_D + P_L \quad (4)$$

Constraints (Inequality)

$$P_{\text{gslack}}^{\min} \leq P_{\text{gslack}} \leq P_{\text{gslack}}^{\max} \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{gi}^{\min} \leq Q_{gi} \leq Q_{gi}^{\max}, i \in N_g \quad (6)$$

$$V_i^{\min} \leq V_i \leq V_i^{\max}, i \in N \quad (7)$$

$$T_i^{\min} \leq T_i \leq T_i^{\max}, i \in N_T \quad (8)$$

$$Q_c^{\min} \leq Q_c \leq Q_c^{\max}, i \in N_c \quad (9)$$

3. MINE BLAST ALGORITHM

Examination of a mine bomb explosion is imitated to design the mine blast algorithm [19-20]. Number of shrapnel pieces (N_s) is considered as the the number of initial population (N_{pop}). First shot point value is generated by a diminutive arbitrarily generated value given as:

$$Y_0 = LB + \text{random} \times (UB - LB) \quad (10)$$

More first shot points are used and it will increase the initial population. It consequently increases the number of function evaluations and the existing location of a mine bomb given as:

$$Y = \{Y_m\}, m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N_d \quad (11)$$

Deliberately N_s shrapnel pieces are created by the mine bomb explosion is the source for another mine to blow up at Y_{n+1} position,

$$Y_{n+1}^f = Y_{e(n+1)}^f + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{m_{n+1}^f}{d_{n+1}^f}}\right) Y_n^f, n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (12)$$

Exploding mine bomb location $Y_{e(n+1)}^f$ is defined as:

$$Y_{e(n+1)}^f = d_n^f \times \text{random} \times \cos(\theta), n = 0,1,2,.. \quad (13)$$

In order to accomplish unvarying search in the domain space the value of θ is set by $360/N_s$ and through this amassing of individuals in a specific region of the area search can be prevented.

Direction of shrapnel pieces m_{n+1}^f and distance d_{n+1}^f are defined as:

$$d_{n+1}^f = \sqrt{(Y_{n+1}^f - Y_n^f)^2 + (F_{n+1}^f - F_n^f)^2} n = 0,1,2,.. \quad (14)$$

$$m_{n+1}^f = \frac{F_{n+1}^f - F_n^f}{y_{n+1}^f - y_n^f} n = 0,1,2, \dots \quad (15)$$

In the solution space exploration is done by:

$$d_{n+1}^f = d_n^f \times (|\text{random } n|)^2 n = 0,1,2,.. \quad (16)$$

$$Y_{e(n+1)}^f = d_n^f \times \cos(\theta), n = 0,1,2,.. \quad (17)$$

Initial distance of shrapnel pieces are reduced gradually to allow the mine bombs search the probable global minimum location in order to amplify the global explore capability of the proposed method. Reduction in d_0^f is given as:

$$d_n^f = \frac{d_{n-1}^f}{\exp(k/\alpha)} \quad n = 1,2,3,.. \quad (18)$$

Exploration and exploitation progression is given as below:

```

If  $\mu > k$ 
Exploration
 $d_{n+1}^f = d_n^f \times (|\text{random } n|)^2 n = 0,1,2,..$ 
 $Y_{e(n+1)}^f = d_n^f \times \cos(\theta), n = 0,1,2,..$ 
Else
Exploitation
 $Y_{e(n+1)}^f = d_n^f \times \text{random} \times \cos(\theta), n = 0,1,2,..$ 
 $d_{n+1}^f = \sqrt{(Y_{n+1}^f - Y_n^f)^2 + (F_{n+1}^f - F_n^f)^2} n = 0,1,2,..$ 
 $m_{n+1}^f = \frac{F_{n+1}^f - F_n^f}{y_{n+1}^f - y_n^f} n = 0,1,2, \dots$ 
 $d_n^f = \frac{d_{n-1}^f}{\exp(k/\alpha)} \quad n = 1,2,3,..$ 
End

```

- a. Initialization of parameters
- b. Condition of exploration factor (μ) is checked
- c. Calculate the distance of shrapnel pieces and their locations by (16) and (17) once the condition of exploration factor is satisfied if not go to Step i.
- d. Direction of shrapnel pieces are calculated by (15).
- e. Shrapnel pieces are produced and their improved locations are calculated by (12).
- f. For engendered shrapnel pieces constraints limits are checked.
- g. Best shrapnel piece is saved as the best sequential solution.
- h. If function value than the best temporal solution is greater than the shrapnel piece? If true, swap the position of the shrapnel piece with the best temporal solution. If not go to Step i.
- i. Distance of shrapnel pieces and their locations are calculated the using (13) and (14) and then return to Step d.
- j. Distance of the shrapnel pieces are reduced by (18).
- k. Verify the convergence criteria and if satisfied, the algorithm will be stopped if not return to Stepb.

4. HARMONY SEARCH ALGORITHM

Harmony search (HS) is a new-fangled population-based metaheuristic optimization algorithm [21] that imitates the music creativity process where the musicians supervise their instruments' pitch by searching for a best state of harmony. The parameters of the HS are: In this step, the solutions are arbitrarily built and reorganize in a reversed order to HM, based on their objective function values such as

$$f(a^1) \leq f(a^2) \dots \leq f(a^{HMS}) . HM = \begin{bmatrix} a_1^1 & \dots & a_N^1 & f(a^1) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \cdot \\ a_1^{HMS} & \dots & a_N^{HMS} & f(a^{HMS}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The following equation concise the two steps i.e. memory consideration and arbitrary consideration.

$$a'_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} a_i \in \{a_i^1, a_i^2, \dots, a_i^{HMS}\} w.p. HMCR \\ a_i \in A_i w.p. (1 - HMCR) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Decision variables (a'_i) are scrutinized and to be tuned with the probability of PAR $\in [0, 1]$ by (21)

$$a'_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} \text{Adjusting pitch w.p. PAR} \\ \text{Doing Nothing w.p. (1 - PAR)} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$(a'_i) = (a_i) \pm \text{rand}() * bw \quad (22)$$

$$a' \in HM \wedge a^{worst} \notin HM \quad (23)$$

The PAR value is linearly increased in iteration's of HS by using the following equation,

$$PAR(gn) = PAR_{min} + \frac{PAR_{max} - PAR_{min}}{NI} \times gn \quad (24)$$

$$bw(gn) = bw_{min} + \frac{bw_{max} - bw_{min}}{NI} \times gn \quad (25)$$

Step a: preliminary population are arbitrarily generated and calculate the fitness of each individual;

Step b: determine the best and the worst individuals in the existing population in HM;

Step c: control a new-fangled harmony: first, engender a novel vector; secondly, adjust the vector through HS;

Step d: modify harmony memory, which is same to selection.

$$x_{i,g+1} = \begin{cases} u_{i,g} \text{ if } (u_{i,g} \leq f(x_{i,g})), \\ x_{i,g} \text{ otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Step e: authenticate the stopping criterion: $|f(best) - f(worst)| < \epsilon = 1 \times 10^{-16}$.

5. HYBRIDIZATION OF MINE BLAST ALGORITHM WITH HARMONY SEARCH ALGORITHM

The hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) improves the search effectively in the solution space. Mine blast algorithm improves the exploration and harmony search algorithm augments the exploitation. At first the proposed algorithm starts with exploration & gradually it moves to the phase of exploitation.

Parameters are initiated

Initial bandwidth of each shrapnel piece will be determined

At first Dynamic Harmony Memory will be nil and in later phases arbitrarily it will be engendered

Objective function has been calculated for the first shot point & Best has been found

```

While (t < Maximum Iterations)
For i= 1: N
If t <  $\mu$  %; Exploration Phase is done by the MBA
Estimate the modernized position of landmines using:

$$Y_{n+1}^f = Y_{e(n+1)}^f + \exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{m_{n+1}^f}{d_{h+1}^f}}\right) Y_n^f, n = 0,1,2,3,..$$

Else
% (HS is embedded in this Exploitation Phase,)
jrandom= floor(D *rand(0, 1));
End for
For j  $\in$  1, ...,D do
If random(0, 1)  $\leq$  CR or j==jrand) then
uj= xj;r0 + F*(xj;r1- xj;r2);
Else
uj= xj;i;
End if
End for
Else
Compute the location of explode landmine by the following

$$X_{e(n+1)}^f = d_n^f \times \text{rand} \times \cos(\theta), n = 0,1,2,..$$

Estimate the Euclidean distance & compute the modernized position of shrapnel pieces
End if
End for
End if

```

Determine objective function of engendered shrapnel pieces and class the shrapnel pieces

Choose the most excellent shrapnel piece

```

// Harmony memory considering: arbitrarily select any variable-i pitch in HM
if (rand(0, 1)  $\leq$  HMCR then
if (round(0, 1)  $\leq$  PAR then
//Pitch adjusting: arbitrarily adjust uj within a small bandwidth,
trand(0, 1) *BAND
if(round(0, 1)  $\leq$  0.5 then
vj= uj+ random(0, 1) *BAND
else
vj= uj- random(0, 1) *BAND
end if
end if
else
//Random playing: arbitrarily select any pitch within upper uj and lower bounds lj
vj= lj+ rand(0, 1) *(uj- lj)
End if
End for
if vjis better than the worst harmony in HM, xworst, then
Replace xworst with vj in HM, then sort HM
End if
Until (best) - f(worst) | <  $\epsilon$ 
End for
End if
End if
End while

```

6. SIMULATION RESULTS

At first in standard IEEE 14 bus system the validity of the proposed hybridized algorithm (MH) has been tested & comparison results are presented in Table 1. Figure 1. Provide the details of Comparison of real power loss.

Table 1. Comparison results

Control variables	ABCO [22]	IABCO [22]	Projected MH
V1	1.06	1.05	1.04
V2	1.03	1.05	1.02
V3	0.98	1.03	1.03
V6	1.05	1.05	1.01
V8	1.00	1.04	0.90
Q9	0.139	0.132	0.110
T56	0.979	0.960	0.920
T47	0.950	0.950	0.900
T49	1.014	1.007	1.000
Ploss (MW)	5.92892	5.50031	4.82426

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Figure 1. Comparison of real power loss

Then IEEE 300 bus system [18] is used as test system to validate the performance of the hybridized algorithm (MH). Table 2 shows the comparison of real power loss obtained after optimization. Figure 2 gives the comparison of real power values. Real power loss has been considerably reduced when compared to the other standard reported algorithms.

Then hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) has been tested in IEEE 30 bus system [25] with considering voltage stability index. It has a sum of active and reactive power consumption of 2.834 and 1.262 per unit on 100 MVA base. Table 3 gives the constraints of control variables; Table 4 gives the system parameters; then Table 5 gives the real power loss comparison. Comparison of different algorithms with reference to voltage stability improvement has been given in Table 6. Then Comparison of values with reference to Voltage Deviation Minimization has been given Table 7. Finally, Comparison of values with reference to Multi – objective formulation is given in Table 8.

Table 2. Comparison of real power loss

Parameter	Method EGA [24]	Method EEA [24]	Method CSA [23]	Projected MH
PLOSS (MW)	646.2998	650.6027	635.8942	618.0414

Figure 2. Real power loss comparison

Table 3. Constraints of control variables

Variables	Minimum (PU)	Maximum (PU)
Generator Voltage	0.95	1.1
Transformer Tap	0.9	1.1
VAR Source	0	5 (MVAR)

Table 4. System parameters

Description	IEEE 30 bus
NB – number of buses	30
NG- Number of generators	6
NT- number of transformers	4
NQ- number of shunt	9
NE- Number of branches	41
PLOSS (base case) MW	5.66
Base care for VD (PU)	0.58217

Table 5. Comparison of real power loss with different metaheuristic algorithms

	DE [26]	GSA [27]	APOPSO [28]	MH
VG1	1.1	1.071	1.100	1.093
VG2	1.09	1.022	1.084	1.040
VG5	1.07	1.040	1.056	1.024
VG8	1.07	1.051	1.076	1.041
VG11	1.1	0.977	1.091	1.083
VG13	5	0.968	1.100	0.970
QC 10	5	1.653	5.000	4.962
QC 12	5	4.3722	5.000	5.000
QC 15	5	0.1199	4.879	4.783
QC 17	5	2.0876	4.976	4.971
QC 20	4.41	0.357	3.821	3.705
QC 21	5	0.2602	4.541	4.662
QC 23	2.8004	0.0000	2.354	2.400
QC 24	5	1.3839	4.654	4.501
QC 29	2.5979	0.0000	2.175	2.160
T11	1.04	1.0985	1.029	1.014
(6-9)				
T12	0.9097	0.9824	0.911	0.905
(6-10)				
T15	0.98	1.095	0.952	0.946
(4-12)				
T36	0.9689	1.0593	0.958	0.943
(28-27)				
PLoss (MW)	4.555	4.5143	4.398	4.214
VD (PU)	1.9589	0.87522	1.047	1.031
L-index (PU)	0.5513	0.14109	0.1267	0.1202

Table 6. Comparison of different algorithms with reference to voltage stability improvement

	DE [26]	GSA [27]	APOPSO [28]	MH
VG1	1.01	0.983	1.011	1.024
VG2	0.99	1.044	1.001	1.012
VG5	1.02	1.020	1.014	1.013
VG8	1.02	0.999	1.009	1.014
VG11	1.01	1.077	0.954	0.935
VG13	1.03	1.044	1.000	1.003
QC 10	4.94	0	4.102	4.102
QC 12	1.0885	0.4735	2.124	2.121
QC 15	4.9985	5	4.512	4.493
QC 17	0.2393	0	0.000	0.000
QC 20	4.99	5	5.000	5.000
QC 21	4.90	0	5.000	5.000
QC 23	4.9863	4.9998	5.000	5.000
QC 24	4.9663	5	5.000	5.000
QC 29	2.2325	5	4.120	4.134
T11	1.02	0.9	0.998	0.976
(6-9)				
T12	0.9038	1.1	0.822	0.805
(6-10)				
T15	1.01	1.051	0.954	0.933
(4-12)				
T36	0.9635	0.9619	0.958	0.942
(28-27)				
PLoss (MW)	6.4755	6.9117	5.698	5.411
VD (PU)	0.0911	0.0676	0.087	0.062
L-index (PU)	0.14352	0.1349	0.1377	0.1310

Table 7. Comparison with reference to Voltage Deviation Minimization

	DE [26]	GSA [27]	APOPSO [28]	MH
VG1	1.09	1.1	1.043	1.031
VG2	1.09	1.1	1.061	1.053
VG5	1.09	1.1	1.061	1.034
VG8	1.04	1.1	1.057	1.033
VG11	1.09	1.1	1.048	1.042
VG13	0.95	1.1	1.091	1.070
QC 10	0.69	5	0.040	0.041
QC 12	4.7163	5	0.039	0.032
QC 15	4.4931	5	0.038	0.033
QC 17	4.51	5	0.040	0.030
QC 20	4.48	5	0.037	0.031
QC 21	4.60	5	0.009	0.014
QC 23	3.8806	5	0.019	0.013
QC 24	3.8806	5	0.011	0.010
QC 29	3.2541	5	0.001	0.004
T11	0.90	0.9	0.919	0.911
(6-9)				
T12	0.9029	0.9	0.924	0.900
(6-10)				
T15	0.90	0.9	0.938	0.913
(4-12)				
T36	0.936	1.0195	0.924	0.915
(28-27)				
PLoss (MW)	7.0733	4.9752	4.478	4.206
VD (PU)	1.419	0.21579	1.8579	1.8200
L-index (PU)	0.1246	0.13684	0.1227	0.1159

Table 8. Comparison of values with reference to Multi – objective formulation

	APOPSO [28]	MH
VG1	1.020	1.012
VG2	1.033	1.013
VG5	1.000	1.000
VG8	1.004	1.001
VG11	1.032	1.013
VG13	1.028	1.014
QC 10	0.051	0.035
QC 12	0.002	0.001
QC 15	0.044	0.023
QC 17	0.009	0.002
QC 20	0.048	0.021
QC 21	0.041	0.020
QC 23	0.033	0.016
QC 24	0.050	0.037
QC 29	0.015	0.018
T11	1.042	1.044
(6-9)		
T12	0.909	0.902
(6-10)		
T15	1.023	1.011
(4-12)		
T36	0.958	0.925
(28-27)		
PLoss (MW)	4.842	4.722
VD (PU)	1.009	1.001
L-index (PU)	0.1192	0.1179

7. CONCLUSION

In this work Mine Blast Algorithm (MBA) has been intermingled with Harmony Search (HS) algorithm successfully solved the optimal reactive power dispatch problem. The hybridized algorithm (MH) improves the search effectively in the solution space. Mine blast algorithm improves the exploration and harmony search algorithm augments the exploitation. At first the proposed algorithm starts with exploration and gradually it moves to the phase of exploitation. At first the proposed algorithm starts with exploration & gradually it moves to the phase of exploitation. Proposed Hybridized algorithm (MH) has been tested on standard IEEE 14, 300 bus test systems. Real power loss has been reduced considerably by the proposed MH algorithm. Then Hybridized Mine Blast Algorithm with Harmony Search algorithm (MH) are tested in IEEE 30, bus system (with considering voltage stability index)- real power loss minimization, voltage deviation minimization, and voltage stability index enhancement has been attained.

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